

too well defined a term, *turbidity*, so familiar in coagulation effects. Now an interesting observation was made that the coagulation-time curves, corresponding (i) to the incipience of flocculation and turbidity (curves No. 3, 4, 5) and (ii) when these effects were unnoticed (curves 1, 2), belonged essentially to the same family of curves, all characterised by a similar and marked *zonal effect*. Precisely similar observations were made in a number of μ -time curves for coagulation in which the proportion of colloid MnO_2 was varied from 0.2 to 1.0 c.c. mixed (after dilution with water in each case to 1.0 c.c. with 1 c.c. of colloid Fe_2O_3). Since these curves did not show any additional features, only one of them (curve 5) is shown in Fig. 1. Analogous results were obtained earlier (Part XI, *loc. cit.*; cf. also Joshi and Panikkar, *Proc. Acad. Sci. U.P.*, *loc. cit.* also, *J. chim. Phys.*, *loc. cit.*) in the finding that marked changes of viscosity occurred independently of whether the corresponding mixture showed flocculation effect such as the familiar rise in turbidity.

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Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids. Part XIII.
“ Zonal effect ” in the Opacity Changes in the Coagulation of Colloid Manganese Dioxide.

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In Parts XI and XII of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 141, 309; cf. also, *Current Science*, 1936, **4**, 481), it was observed that the change of the refractive index of the above sol during any one of its numerous electrolytic and mutual coagulations examined showed an unmistakable and characteristic ‘*zonal effect*,’ which became more conspicuous, the *slower* the change. The present paper records observations of this effect, it would appear for the first time in the field of coagulation kinetics, in the change of the *opacity* during coagulation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The colloid was prepared and its strength estimated. *viz.*, 1.85 g. MnO_2 per litre, as in Part XI (*loc. cit.*). The opacity during coagulation was measured by use of a sensitive thermopile and a low resistance Broca galvanometer (*cf.* Mukherjee and Majumdar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 757). Light from a 4-volt lamp run at a constant potential from a battery of storage cells was first passed through distilled water in an optical cell in order to eliminate the heat radiation and then allowed to fall on the cell with optically flat surfaces, which contained the coagulating mixture. Intensity of the light transmitted by the sol was indicated by the deflections of the galvanometer. The source of light, the water-filter, the coagulating sol and the thermopile were enclosed in an air thermostat with glass sides. This was almost wholly immersed in water contained in another thermostat with glass sides, except on the top, which was closed by a well fitting cover insulated against heat conduction by thick pads of sheep wool. The outer thermostat was also well covered with pads of wool except on the glass faces which were suitably covered to screen off any stray light. The temperature of this thermostat was kept constant at $23.5 \pm 5^\circ$. Under these conditions the thermopile was found to be well protected against any external radiation and changes of temperature. The galvanometer deflection for the colloid, diluted with an equal amount of water, was found to be 249 mm. When the same amount of the colloid was mixed with an equal volume of a solution of the coagulant employed, *viz.*, potassium chloride, the galvanometer deflection was smaller. The difference of these two deflections was taken as a measure of the opacity of the coagulating sol. These measurements were continued, till it was suspected that the system had become heterogeneous by formation of discrete particles of the coagulum. The seven curves in Fig. 1 show the variation of opacity during coagulations due to solutions of potassium chloride whose concentration before admixture with the sol was varied in the range $N/1$ to $N/20$.

D I S C U S S I O N.

These results show that while on the whole, the opacity of the colloid increased during coagulation, the rate of its increase by increasing the electrolyte concentration was not marked. Substantially similar results were obtained in Part XI in observations of the changes

of refractivity during coagulation. The chief feature of interest of the coagulation-time curves now reported is in the discontinuous or *zonal* variation of opacity, in confirmation of earlier results obtained with viscosity and refractivity measurements. Variation of opacity has been amongst the earliest and widest used properties in the kinetics of coagulation. The observation of the *zonal effect* using such an approved property, therefore, supports the deduction made in Part XII that presumably, the *zonal effect* inheres in the mechanism of coagulation. In agreement with earlier results (Part XI) the opacity-time

FIG. 1.

curves in Fig. 1 show that the *zonal effect* is practically absent in *rapid* coagulations (*cf.* curves for $N/1\text{-KCl}$), and that the number of *zones* and (in the majority of cases) the duration of each *zone* tends to increase by increasing the dilution of the coagulant, *i.e.*, the slower the change. Although a complete theory of the opacity of a coagulating colloid is not available in the literature, it can be anticipated on general considerations, that the (a) effective particle-size and *difference* in the refractive index for the particles and the dispersion medium are its chief determinants. Now, while considerable evidence is afforded by results in Parts XI and XII that at any rate the over-all refractivity of the sol varies *zonally* during coagulation, nothing definite can be stated about changes in the refractive index characteristic of (b) the particles and (c) the medium. (b) would appear to depend upon the refractivity for the dispersed material in its pure state, the extent of its hydration, the nature and the amount of the electrolytic material associated with the "double layer" and especially its electrical condition. (c) is not expected to change sensibly. The difference between (b) and (c), however, is significant and may vary appreciably. More experimental data are, however, needed at the present stage in the general theoretical development of the subject in order to envisage the observed *zonal* variation of opacity in terms of (a) (b) and (c).

The foregoing results have some interest in regard to the suggestion made by numerous workers (*cf.* Freundlich, "Colloid and Capillary Chemistry," 1926, pp. 424-450; also, Desai, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 191) that coagulation is *autocatalytic*. Evidence has been adduced in previous papers in this series (Parts V-IX, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924-36) that autocatalysis can not be a *general* characteristic of coagulation. Now, the curves in Fig. 1 show that the horizontal *zones* are produced more frequently during the earlier stages of coagulation and that this tendency increases with the dilution of the coagulant. These conditions are favourable for autocatalysis as shown by the so-called **S**-shaped curves. It may be suggested, therefore, that the evidence for *autocatalysis* might arise from the presence of these *zones of coagulation* during which the property selected for measuring coagulation is not sensibly affected, and whose combined effect gives the initial section of the coagulation-time curve its low gradient.